

DISCOURSE MARKERS IN IZỌN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the presence and functions of discourse markers in the Izọn language, a Niger-Congo language spoken across six states in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Drawing on both spoken and written data from native speakers, textbooks and dictionaries, the research identified a wide range of discourse markers in Izọn, categorizing them according to contrast, addition, result, time and other functions. The study employed a descriptive methodology, with analysis grounded in coherence theory and relevance theory, to examine how these markers contribute to textual cohesion, guide interpretation, and manage the flow of discourse. Findings revealed that Izọn discourse markers serve as critical tools for linking ideas, signaling relationships between sentences, expressing speakers' attitudes and enhancing clarity in communication. The study underscores the universality of discourse markers across languages and highlights their indispensable role in ensuring coherence, fluency, and effective communication in both spoken and written Izọn discourse.

Key words: Izọn, discourse, discourse markers, dialect, coherence, etc.

INTRODUCTION

The study of language has come a long way and can be viewed from different perspectives. Several scholars have looked at it from the angle of sounds, words, combination of words to form structures, meaning of words, sentence types and patterns, etc. Others are: the dynamism of language, contextual analysis of usage including the bond between the speakers and their language because language cannot occur in isolation. So, people use language for different purposes in their daily activities.

Society thrives on language and language is made up of words, thus, a group of people living together in a place harmoniously would as a matter of fact interact. The use of linguistic devices in writing or speech tend to make it aesthetically appealing. Normally, in every conversation or

writing words and phrases are used to connect ideas, opinions, suggestions even several sentences so as to guide the flow. These words or phrases are called discourse markers.

Discourse markers can also be used to indicate a change in topic, express an attitude or simply connect thoughts and sentences. Here are some examples of discourse markers; thus, well, so, however, nevertheless, moreover, and, but, in addition, furthermore, etc. These words and phrases tend to act as adhesives between ideas, thereby helping to create coherence and clarity in both spoken or written discourse. Invariably, one can see them as signposts that guides the listeners or readers through the thoughts of the speaker or writer.

However, the likelihood of the presence of these lexical elements in languages worldwide may not be ruled out. This is due to the fact that when people talk, they usually pause to think, enumerate items, point out similarities, draw a contrast or change the direction of the conversation and sum up the discourse in their various languages. All these are achieved with the help of discourse markers, though the way and manner of their presentation in both spoken discourse and written texts may differ from language to language. In other words, the exact words or phrases of discourse markers vary across languages but the inherent functions remain the same. Apart from English language other international languages like French, Spanish, etc also portray traces of discourse markers. For instance, in French, “alors” meaning “so” and “donec” meaning “therefore” are often used as discourse markers. Likewise in Spanish, “bueno” meaning “well” and “entonces” meaning “then” also serve similar purposes.

In the same vein, discourse markers also exist in Nigerian indigenous languages. Nigeria has multiple languages and has not been able to develop or adopt a common indigenous language as its official language. The government of Nigeria recognises three major languages that can be used at the national level. They are; Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba with a lot of scholarly publications. Language experts from the above major ethnic groups have identified some discourse markers that have infiltrated into Nigerian English. Here are some examples: Hausa – “ba” for emphasis, Igbo “biko” meaning please and Yoruba – “sha” for attention. These lexical items are common among speakers of Nigerian English from the various regions where they are located.

Moreover, Nigerian government acknowledges the importance of language hence encourages the development of other indigenous languages. This can be attested to in the language policy spelt out in the National Policy on Education, 2004. It is clearly stated thus “... and to this end, government will develop the orthography for many more Nigerian languages and produce textbooks in Nigerian languages...” From the foregoing, articles such as this are written in a bid to promote the native languages in line with the language policy. Hence, the researchers embarked on this study to ascertain the existence of discourse markers in Izon language, an indigenous language spoken in the Niger-Delta area of Nigeria.

THE LOCATION OF THE IZON LANGUAGE

The Izon language is spoken in the Niger-Delta area of Nigeria. It cuts across six states in the south-south geo-political zone. The states are: Bayelsa, Delta, Edo, Ondo, Rivers and Akwa-Ibom state. The Izon language belongs to the large African Niger-Congo family. According to Evilewuru (2013) the Izon ethnic group is made up of sixty-three clans. Among these clans the Izon and Ijoid speakers co-exist and the affinity between them is such that they share both cultural and religious traditions.

The Izon nation comprises different sub-groups called “Ibes”. Each “Ibe” or sub-group has its own dialect. Consequently, the dialects used in this article are; “Kabou” which is spoken in Sagbama local government area of Bayelsa state and Patani local government area of Delta state including the “Kolokuma” dialect that is used in Bayelsa state. The “Kolokuma” dialect is spoken in Kolokuma-Opokuma local government area of Bayelsa state. It is the dialect of education as well as electronic media in Bayelsa state. In all, “Kabou” and “Kolokuma” dialects are mutually intelligible.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Generally, human beings use language as a means of communication in their day-to-day dealings. In most discourse, certain lexical items are used to make it colourful and achieve unity of thought. Thus, the relevance and use of discourse markers in every spoken or written text cannot be overemphasized. To this end, this article seeks to investigate the presence of discourse markers in Izon language.

AIM

The overall aim of this study is to examine the existence of discourse markers/sentence connectors in Izon language.

OBJECTIVES

Specifically, the objectives of this article are:

- I. To identify discourse markers in Izon language
- II. To state the functions of discourse markers in both spoken and written texts in Izon language.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW OF DISCOURSE MARKERS

According to Jorgensen, and Philip, (2002) the term, discourse has become vague, either meaning almost nothing, or being used with more precise, but rather different meanings in different contexts. They maintained that in many cases, underlying the word ‘discourse’ is the general idea that language is structured according to different patterns that people’s utterances follow when they take part in different domains of social life, such as ‘medical discourse’, ‘political discourse’, ‘linguistic discourse’, etc. Be that as it may, they proposed a preliminary definition of a discourse as a particular way of talking about and understanding the world (or aspect of the world)

Following this line of thought, discourse is more or less an extended verbal expression given by an individual in course of communication. It could be a written text or an extended communication that could be interactive dealing with some particular topic. Such conversations or written speeches are often marked by lexical items like words and phrases called discourse markers. They act as glue thereby bringing out the beauty and making the talk to cohere.

Thus, Ibibi, (2018) explained that discourse is a language structure beyond analysis of sentences and it can also be seen as pieces of language larger than sentence that function together to convey a given idea or information. She went further to state that the linguistic devices that are used to bind these pieces of language or expression together are called discourse markers.

Brown and Levinson (1987) cited in Ibbi, (2018) asserted that discourse markers are key features of both formal and informal native speaker language. Does this mean that non-native speakers cannot use discourse markers? The writers of this empirical research are of the view that non-native speakers that are eloquent in the language can also use discourse markers either formally or informally. Nevertheless, the ability to use discourse markers tend to indicate a higher level of fluency and creativity that sustains the interest of the listeners and perhaps the readers of that given text. Though Blackemore (1987) disclosed that they are used less frequently in speech unless the speech is very formal.

In another development, discourse markers could be seen as link words or sentence connectives especially in writing and can be described as the fillers that bind together the piece of writing and making the different parts of the text to come together. Consequently, writers use them to link ideas or information in a discourse. In line with the above, Gerald as was cited by Ibbi, (2018) is of the opinion that discourse are words like 'however', 'although', and 'nevertheless', which are more commonly referred to as 'linking words' and 'linking phrases', or 'sentence connectors'. These lexical items are seen as the 'glue' that binds together a piece of writing, making the different parts of the text 'stick' together. The appropriate and sufficient use of discourse markers in a piece of writing makes the text to be logically constructed and the connections between the different sentences and paragraphs easy to understand. They also help the reader to predict the direction of the flow of discourse than linking the various text elements especially in spoken discourse.

In view of the fact that discourse markers are crucial in understanding a message Blackemore (1987) observed that discourse markers guide the hearers in finding the most relevant interpretation in the given context by constraining the number of possible interpretations. In addition, she declared that there is no consensus among language scholars as to what discourse markers are and the exact discourse markers in English language. This assertion is made probably owing to the dynamic nature of language. According to Ibbi, (2018) some scholars have used such terms as pragmatic markers, discourse connective or discourse particles to describe discourse markers, though it is difficult to conclude that they all refer to the same thing. Blackemore (1987) in her text, provided some examples of discourse markers in English such as 'well', 'but', 'so', 'include', 'in other words', 'as a result', 'now', etc.

Furthermore, Fraser (1998) sees discourse markers as 'prepositional phrase' with certain exceptions that signal a relationship between the segments they introduce. He continued by saying that discourse markers have a core meaning which usually is not conventional and their more specific interpretation is negotiated by the context, both linguistics and conceptual. The role they play in any text or speech is basically grammatical in the sense that they link ideas and connect the entire text or speech thereby achieving cohesion and coherence.

Moreover, as earlier stated in this paper the likelihood of the preclusion of discourse markers in languages worldwide cannot be overemphasized. Instances of the use of discourse markers in international languages like French, Spain, English are cited in this article. Other common discourse markers in French language are: "et" = and, "de plus" = furthermore, "aussi" = also, "par ailleurs" = moreover, "en outre" = besides, "pourtant", etc. = yet/however/nevertheless/though/nonetheless/even so/ all the same/however good depending on the context. Anyway, the proficient use of these and other discourse markers is a key step towards achieving fluency as they play a crucial role in structuring clear and persuasive

discourse in French. Similarly, in Spanish language discourse markers are called pragmatic words or phrases. The following are some examples of discourse markers in the Spanish language: “mira/oye” = look/listen- they serve to draw the attention of the listeners’, “pues” = functions as well to connect ideas or introduces a new turn in the conversation, “primero/en primer lugar” = first/firstly used in ordering information, “por ejemplo” = for example, “o sea” = or rather/that is to say- used to clarify or rephrase what was just said, “digo” = I mean to say- used for explanation/clarification, “ahorabien”, etc = now then – is a more formal way to signal a transition.

For English language, a detail but not exhaustive analysis of the review of available literature on discourse markers in different categories is stated in table 1 and 2 below.

TABLE 1: Discourse Markers

ADDITION	COMPARISON	CONTRAST	TIME	RESULT
Too	Equally	Conversely	In the past	As a result,
Again	Likewise,	At the same time	Presently	Then
Moreover	In the same way	On the other hand,	At last,	Accordingly,
In addition,	Comparable,	On the contrary	Finally,	Consequently
Additionally,	Another x like	Instead	Immediately	Thus
Then	Similarly,	Notwithstanding	Currently	Thereupon
First, Second, etc	Just as ... So too	Alternatively,	At that time	Hence
Further	A similar x	Nevertheless	Subsequently	In consequence
Besides	As with	Though	Eventually	So
Furthermore	Comparatively	Otherwise	Thereafter	Therefore
Equally important	In the same vein	Even so	In the meantime,	Base on this
Also	In like manner	Nonetheless	Meanwhile	Due to this
Next	As well as	However,	At this point	Owing to this

TABLE 2: Discourse Markers

PLACE	EXAMPLE	SUMMARY
Nearby	Specifically,	After all,
Here	As revealed by	In brief
In the front	That is	In other words,
There	Such as	In general,
Next to	For instance,	Clearly
At that point	Illustrated by	Anyway
Opposite to	For example,	In sum
Adjacent to	An instance of this	In short
On the other side	For one thing	To be sure
Beyond	This can be seen in	It seems
In the back	In particular	On the whole

At this juncture, it is imperative to briefly review any available literature on discourse markers in Nigerian native languages. Accordingly, Nigerian indigenous languages also portray discourse markers. Below are some examples of discourse markers from the native languages used in Nigeria.

“Abi” is a Yoruba discourse marker signifying agreement.

“Jare”/ “Jor” is a mitigation and emphasis marker used in Yoruba.

“Shebi”/ “Shey” is an agreement seeking marker used in Yoruba language.

“Ehn”/ “Ehen” is a discourse marker in Yoruba language that functions as phatic and emotive interjections.

“Sha” is a Yoruba discourse attention seeking and mitigation marker.

“O” is an emphasis and mitigation marker used in Yoruba, Ishan and Igbo languages

“Biko” is an Igbo discourse marker meaning please. It is a mitigation/emphasis marker.

“Ngwanu” is used in Igbo language indicating acceptance as in ok/agreement

“má” and “ká” for object focus

“weé”, na and “ga” for verb focus

“gwań” and “ghi” for sentence focus. Other suffixes like “tú” which shows temporal or spatial relationships, honorifics or diminutive forms.

“Fa” is a Hausa emphasis marker.

“Ba” is used in Hausa language for emphasis. That is, if the person spoken to understands what is being said.

“Na wa” is a modified Hausa expression of “na wahala”. It is an emotive interjection used as a discourse marker.

“Shikena” is a cognitive interjection marker used in Hausa language.

From the above, one can see the presence of discourse markers in Nigerian languages such as Yoruba, Hausa, Igbo, Ishan, etc. Similarly, the existence of these lexical items in Izon language cannot be foreclosed.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

The theories adopted in this study are coherence theory and relevance theory. Coherence theory harps on the importance of unity of thoughts, ideas, statements, etc in a text or discourse. Thus, discourse markers are seen as key elements that contribute to this connectedness by indicating the relationships between different parts of the discourse. Scholars associated with this theory are Schiffrin, Redeker, Fraser and Lenk.

Moreover, Schiffrin’s model as was cited in google AI for instance, proposes five levels of discourse coherence. They are; exchangeable structure, behavioural structure, conceptual structure, participation frame and information state. However, this model has been criticized

severally by scholars for its limited validity and explanatory power. In all, coherence theory upholds the crucial nature of discourse markers for establishing textual coherence.

The second theory used in this study is relevance theory. The proponents of this theory are Spencer and Wilson. Relevance theory concerns itself on how speakers and hearers achieve the best possible way to understand themselves easily in a discourse. It tends to view discourse markers as signals that guide the hearer's interpretation process by indicating the most relevant context for understanding a speech. In this theory discourse markers are seen as 'sign posts' that constrain the context selection and interpretation of other statements made in the process of communication. For instance, 'well' is a discourse marker that signals the most immediate accessible context which may not be the most relevant one for understanding the utterances that follows it. Other scholars associated with this approach are: Blackemore, Rouchota and Jucker. Comparatively, relevance theory seems to furnish us with a more unified explanation for various uses of discourse markers than coherence centred approach.

In this article, both theories are apt because coherence emphasizes the importance of text cohesion with the help of discourse markers while relevance theory analyzes discourse markers as pointers guiding the hearers' interpretation and understanding of a discourse based on a given context.

METHODOLOGY

The method employed in this research is descriptive based on the topic. This method is adopted because the lexical items in the Izon language are presented in the way they exist in the language without any form of manipulation.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The data for this study were collected using the fieldwork method. The researchers, being native speakers were able to interact with their people in addition to textbooks written in Izon language including Izon dictionaries to collect the needed data. Data was extracted from the following textbook and dictionaries: Centre for Niger Delta studies (2014) / (2015) / (2016) "Izon Go Fun", Bayelsa state Ministry of Education (2003) Izon – English glossary in the Junior Secondary curriculum for Izon, Williamson and Bleach (2011) Izon dictionary based on the "kolokuma" dialect, Agbegha (1996) Izon – English dictionary based on the "mein" dialect and Evilewuru (2013) Izon Beeli dictionary.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The simple descriptive approach was employed in the analysis of the data. As native speakers, the statements where the sentence connectors occur are written from the spoken discourse of indigenous users of the language with interpretation. Similarly, discourse markers are also extracted from various passages of written texts in Izon language and analysed with interpretations using the coding scheme for text analysis.

DATA PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION

The various discourse markers in Izon are presented in different groups. This is done for easy identification.

Table 3: Contrast/Summary Discourse markers in Izon

Contrast	Dialect	Meaning	Summary	Dialect	Meaning
Aniakpo	Kabou	Or	Tuubi	Both dialects	At last, finally
Aniabikpo	Kabou	However,	Kiisimo	Kabou	Briefly
Anikjaniabikpo	Kabou	Nevertheless	Fa korobi	kolokuma	In conclusion
Enja	Kolokuma	However,	O gba yo se bi	Kabou	All he has said
Inda	Kolokuma	But			
Minj	Kolokuma	While			
Eni kpo	kolokuma	Even then			

Table 4: Addition/Result Discourse markers in Izon

Addition	Dialect	Meaning	Result	Dialect	Meaning
Mo Mo	Kolokuma	And	Tubi	Kabou	Because/the reason
Manj	Kolokuma	And	Anj bimejini	Kabou	Because of that
Ani buomobi	Kabou	After that one	Bei tuumo bimejini	kolokuma	For these reasons
Bei buomobi	Kabou	After this one	Bei bolou duomo bei	Kabou	From henceforth
Zinj	Kabou	Another	Eni bimejin ni	kolokuma	Because of that
Bei boomo	kolokuma	After this	Bei gba buomodou yemo	kolokuma	From the aforementioned
Beimo bo boobi	kolokuma	After these events			
Bei ye boobi	kolokuma	After this incident			

Table 5: Time/Other Discourse markers in Izon

Time	Dialect	Meaning	Others	Dialect	Meaning
Bei ifie se	Kolokuma	All the time	Kangha timiyan	Kabou	Possibly
Tijekiribi	Kolokuma	Right now, /now	Vi	Kolokuma	other
kenj seri labi	Both dialects	At that particular time	Gba ka kpo	Kabou	No matter how
kenj ifie	✓	There was a time	Aba	kolokuma	If
kenj aladou ifie	✓	Once upon a time	Gba mej bi de bia	Kabou	One can categorically say
Biemi biemi	✓	Right now, / now - emphasis	Gba mej bia	Kabou	Having said so
Biemikpo	✓	Currently/presently/ Even now/right now	Vorora/vororapaa	kolokuma	Suddenly

Tue-ife	✓	Later/subsequently	Boḍeḍi baibi	Kabou	Yesterday
Tuubi	✓	At last,	Gbeṣe	Kabou	Precisely/exactly
keṇibai labi	✓	One particular day	Gbeṣe gba me bia	Kabou	As a matter of fact,
Kanko	✓	Shortly			
Bolou ifie, mamu karamu ifie,	✓	Firstly, secondly, etc			
Bei ifie labi	✓	By this time			
Gba sin daaba	✓	After you have finished			

DISCUSSION

Evidently, the above data signifies that Iḗon language is replete with discourse markers and they can be categorized into various groups as can be seen from the above tables. All things being equal, every language user that wants to create a lasting impression in the minds of his/her listeners or readers knows the importance of discourse markers in speech or writing. As a result, the existence of discourse markers in the Iḗon language and the basic functions they perform in every spoken or written discourse is the same in all languages.

Thus, as native speakers that have listened to various users of the language including the textbooks used in this empirical research, one can see that Iḗon discourse markers guide the listener or reader with a view of making them to understand the relationship of the various parts of a discourse or text in terms of cause and effect, addition or contrast, etc. For instance, in a sentence like “**bei tuumoḍ bimeḗn ni**, tisaotumoḍ kiḗikiḗi bara aki na owoḗmoḍ toluḗonghimi.” It means for these reasons; the teachers will teach the children very well. Looking at the sentence one can deduce that reasons have been given why teachers should do their job. Other discourse markers showing cause and effect are; **bei bolou duomo bei** = from hence forth, **eni bimeḗn ni**, = because of this, etc. Equally important are addition markers that guide the flow of a conversation such as **bei boḗomo** = after this, **beimo bo boḗobi**, = after these incidents, **eni kpo** = even then, etc.

In as much as discourse markers direct the course of a spoken or written discourse, they also connect ideas so as to unify the overall text. This point reinforces coherence theory used in this research claim that discourse markers are key elements that signals relationships between different parts of the text in achieving coherence. In consequence, Iḗon discourse markers like every other sentence connector in languages across board help to create smooth transition between thoughts and ideas thereby making the entire text to be more cohesive. This can be seen in the following sentences in Iḗon: Arḗ keṇi naira oḗizi aki na ḍa fun-ama feṅghimi. **Vi** keṇi naira oḗizibi arḗ ma aki na fiyaj feḗ fimi. Meaning: I will use one thousand naira to buy some books. The other one thousand naira I will use it to buy food to eat. The sentence connector “vi” meaning other is used. **Tḗkiri** means immediately/ right now/now. Thus: Eri **tḗkiri** wo iḗio ḡo

tonmì. Meaning; he immediately planned it in his mind. Other words are: **bièmi bièmi** = currently/presently, **tue-ifie** = later/subsequently, etc.

Furthermore, as humans we use language to express ourselves. The use of discourse markers tends to express the speaker's or writer's attitude towards what is being said or written. It is interesting to note that orators or good public speakers have an inclination to use discourse markers appropriately to drive their points home. In line with relevance theory, one of the theories adopted in this article upholds the view that discourse markers are signposts that guides both listeners' and readers' interpretation processes towards understanding the speaker's or writer's line of thought. An instance of this is the use of addition discourse markers and contrast markers in Izo language by native speakers of the language. Itobo boumọ sẹ bowei beni **mọ** osuo beni **mọ** inegha. **mọ mọ** = and. Bowie beni **kan-ko** serii mọ itobo biledọ. **kan-ko** = as soon as/shortly. It means; farm lands by the river banks cannot withstand flood and rain water. As soon as flood rises, farm lands by the river banks are flooded. Contrast markers such as “**enja**” = however. **Enja** ọrọ ama bọ taniimi olokomọ seigha. Meaning = however, the laws they enact in their town is not bad. These and other discourse markers are used by orators gliding from one point to the other in a bid to express themselves before their audience.

This leads us to the fact that discourse markers manage the flow of conversation between interlocutors. These lexical items categorised in the tables above in Izo language are used to indicate a pause thereby taking time to think and possibly change the direction of a conversation or enumerate items, etc while discussing.

On the whole, these linguistic units called discourse markers are very relevant in grasping the trend and coherence of spoken or written language. Next, they enable the listeners and readers interpret the author's intentions, follow the development of ideas and make sense of the whole message. These words or phrases play a major role in the adaptation of language specific contexts as well as the communicative needs of the interlocutors involved in the discourse.

In reality, Izo language discourse markers alongside others in languages of the world enhances the dynamic and flexible nature of language use including how speakers and writers normally adjust their language to fit the circumstances that is imminent.

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